

SPΦ-DETERMINISM: IMPACT ON ATOM IS CAUSE MODERN GLOBAL NATURAL CATACLISMS

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Abstract

To date, an analysis similar to this has not yet been carried out. And this is in spite of all the available scientific prerequisites for identifying a close causal connection between phenomena, at first glance, which have no points of contact. The absence is primarily due to psychological reasons than any other serious objective reasons. It is the human psychology of the world perception, in turn, which forms the modern scientific paradigm, is thus an insurmountable barrier to the expansion of the scientific outlook. The incompleteness of the understanding of the fundamental nature of the deterministic nature of the world around it and all its processes threaten humanity with unprecedented misfortunes - for not knowing the law is no excuse from responsibility. The current modern natural anomalies are only weak precursors of the impending planetary catastrophe.

Keywords: determinism, symmetry, Fibonacci series, golden section, SPΦ-symmetry, holographic principle, atom, the core of the planet.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Physics of intersystem interaction: coefficient of similarity between an atom and a planet.

The principle of symmetry in astrophysics

The purpose of this article is to identify the essence of the mechanism provoking modern global natural disasters. Today, this mechanism has not been discovered by modern science, and therefore scientists see anything as the cause of a wide range of natural disasters and rapid climate change - from the greenhouse effect to the cyclical nature of geological periods. The now prevailing theory of relativity and the atomistic paradigm, through the prism of which the world around us and its phenomena are analyzed today, have exhausted themselves and inhibit progress. The impossibility of conducting proper analysis and discovery of the true causes of modern natural disasters lies in ignoring and rejecting by academic science the latest fundamental works, which undoubtedly deserve close attention of the scientific world. Among such advanced fundamental works, the author, in the first place, considers the works of David Bohm, Karl Prybram, Gerardus Hooft, the Russian scientist Sergey Fedosin, the experiments of Alan Aspect, as well as many other eminent scientists.

As we were able to find out in the previous article [1], the planet is a collective of elementary particles forming it. Consequently, there must be a definite connection between the elementary particle and the whole object called the planet. Intersystem interaction is based on the similarity of the radii of the orbits of the Solar and atomic systems in relation to each other. In addition, it is assumed that the Solar System and atomic systems are mutually receiving and transmitting information and energy structures, where the values of the orbit radii are taken not in absolute value, but in atomic and astronomical units. In turn, the radii are the amplitudes of the waves in the receiving-transmitting structures. Therefore, the Solar System, as a receiving structure, perceives the atomic system transmitting information. And vice versa. This principle is based on the physics of intersystem interaction, presented today by the theory of synchronization and the theory of infinite nesting of matter. The physics of intersystem interaction is the physics of wave exchange, based on the similarity of amplitudes, the magnitude of which is equal to the radii of the planets in astronomical units and at the same time expressed in conventional units that characterize the radii of the electron orbits. This kind of interaction substantiates the information and energy exchange, both at the macro level: between objects on Earth and within the Solar System, and between scale levels: between an atom and a planet. According to the intersystem interaction described by $SP\Phi$ -symmetry and vibration mechanics, different objects, despite individual different rhythms, and, at first glance, very weak links with each other, nevertheless, produce a single and stable co-existence rhythm.

1. Elementary particles with their own atomic frequency – (hereinafter: OAF) and, the corresponding stationary waves, enter into a common rhythm. A new system is formed – an atom, with a single frequency equal to the sum of the frequencies of particle motions forming it.
2. The same systems – atoms again enter into a single coordinated rhythm. The system is formed again – the molecule, where the former enters as an integral part.
3. Further, the molecules form a conglomerate of matter with a frequency equal to the sum of the frequencies of the atoms.
4. Substances in general – the matter of a single planet, which has its own cosmic frequency (hereinafter: OSF); ω_0 – frequency of periodic rotation around its own axis and a star per cycle. In other words, the array of elementary particles i forming the planet produces a single coordinated rhythm, starting from the electron rotation frequency in the stationary state and further, finally expressed in ω_0 – the cyclic rotation frequency of the planet around its axis and the star, which means that ω_0 – is the collective resultant frequency [2]. From the position of wave mechanics, the electron and the planet are standing spherical waves. [3], [4] From the

perspective of the theory of infinite nesting of matter (hereinafter: TINM), an electron and a planet are a manifestation of the mechanism of the law of conservation of universal energy E , realized in the wave λ of matter m , at different levels of existence. The difference is solely in the scale of objects and, accordingly, in the degeneracy of the substance of objects. As we determined [1]: the essence of matter m as such is condensed absolute energy E in the form of a rotating electromagnetic field, which manifests itself both as waves and as elementary particles. That is, the realization of E in matter m occurs in accordance with the law of conservation of energy, expressed by the spin-orbital characteristics of elementary particles. In the case of an electron, this is the minimal single wave of E . The planet is an astrophysical object, a group of elementary particles i , its components, at a minimum, stable protons and electrons. Thus, in accordance with the virial theorem [5] and the principle of determinism [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], the planet is the sum of the quantum-mechanical energies of atomic-sized cells:

$E_0 \sum_i mc^2$, or a set of electronic (non-divergent) wave packets of elementary particles:

$E_0 \sum_i \Psi_{\text{planet}}$ – the resulting wave of waves of universal energy E has taken a spherical shape.

That is, according to $SP\Phi$ -symmetry, between the frequency ω of the electron in the first Bohr orbit and own space frequency (OSF) of the Earth ω_0 there is a direct correlation (coefficient of similarity), revealed the mathematical apparatus of $SP\Phi$ -symmetry. Let us find frequency ω of rotation of the electron in the first Bohr orbit:

$$\omega = \frac{v_1}{2\pi r_1} = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi m r_1^2}, \quad \omega = 3.7 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ Hz.}$$

The accuracy ratio is not worse than 2%, which is clearly an indicator of intersystem interaction. Thus, between OSF ω_0 of Earth (365.25) and the cyclic frequency ω of rotation of the electron in the atom (OAF) in the stationary state ($3.7 \cdot 10^{15}$) revealed similarity coefficient equal to $1 \cdot 10^{\pm 13}$, which is the number of the Fibonacci series (namely rate 13). This again demonstrates intersystem interactions – about energy and wave exchange between collective of atoms forming planet and its mutual synchronization of vibrations:

$$\text{OAF} \leftarrow 1 \cdot 10^{\pm 13} \rightarrow \text{OSF}$$

Consequently, based on the cyclic rotation frequency ω_0 of Mars (668.59) and the Earth (365, 25), the length of the first Bohr orbit of the Martian electrons is 54.6% more than the Earth's. From this it is obvious that the difference in the rotation periods, also in percentage, is a number from the Fibonacci series: $\lceil 54,6 \rceil = 55$. This once again confirms the validity of the Butusov hypothesis. [13] It follows a quite logical conclusion about the inequality (dissymmetry) of the quantum properties of matter (space-time) of the Earth to the quantum properties of matter

(space-time) of both Mars and other planets of the Solar System, except for the Moon, which is synchronized with the Earth in orbital resonance 1: 1 [14]. In other words, the Moon is symmetric with the Earth according to the quantum properties of matter. Thus, the patterns of «golden» symmetry are manifested both between the atom and their collective – the planet, as well as between the periodic frequencies of rotation of the planets of the solar system themselves.

It should be noted that Pierre Curie published an article in 1884 on the orderliness and repeatability that underlie the study of crystal symmetry. In it, he formulated a series of deep ideas of symmetry, which have since become classical. One of these ideas argues that it is impossible to consider the symmetry of a body, not taking into account the symmetry of the environment. The paramount importance of these provisions, very perfect for all their simplicity, lies in the fact that the elements of symmetry in question apply to all physical phenomena without exception. The patterns of «golden» symmetry are manifested in the energy transitions of elementary particles, in the structure of some chemical compounds, in planetary and space systems, in the gene structures of living organisms. These patterns, as mentioned above, exist in the structure of individual organs of the person and body as a whole, and also manifest themselves in biorhythms and the functioning of the brain and visual perception. Guided by an in-depth study of symmetry groups that can exist in nature, Pierre Curie showed how to use these provisions as geometrical as physical to predict whether a given phenomenon is possible under these conditions or impossible. At the beginning of one of the articles, he expresses the following statement: *«I believe that the concepts of symmetry customary for crystallographers should be introduced into physics»*. Today it is already obvious that the concepts of symmetry must be introduced into astrophysics. Based on such assumptions, i.e. transferring the effects inherent in the microcosm to the macro level, it can be assumed that hypothetical “black holes” are in fact ordinary stars or globular star clusters whose spectrum is absorbed. That is, we can say that we are dealing with the cosmological effect of Mössbauer.

2. HOLOGRAPHIC PRINCIPLE

In 1982, a group of French researchers discovered that under certain conditions microparticles are able to communicate with each other regardless of the distance between them, which was a practical confirmation of the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen paradox. The American physicist Juan Maldacena in 1997 compiled a series of equations describing the behavior of holographic objects of a universal scale. For the first time the idea that our Universe was arranged according to the holographic principle was put forward in 1993 by the Netherlands physicist Gerard 't Hooft, who was studying black holes. He stated that objects such as universes and black holes can be

represented as a giant two-dimensional hologram. On the surface of the latter, “recorded” information concerning the features of the curvature of space-time inside the object. This allows us to perceive it as a three-dimensional sphere.

The holographic principle is reminiscent of the Platonic allegory of the cave and consists of two main statements:

1. All information contained in a certain area of space can be represented as a «hologram» – a theory that «lives» on the border of this area.
2. The theory on the borders of the studied area of space should contain, at the most, one degree of freedom per a Planck area.

This hypothesis is a continuation of the studies of David Bohm and Karl Pribram, who suggested that at a deep level of reality that is not subject to direct observation and measurement, the Universe is a hologram. Understanding the world as a huge hologram was the result of scientific discoveries in the twentieth century, which shook the stability of scientific authorities. One of the most significant scientific events of the last century was the discovery of wave-corpuscle dualism. But for science, the phenomenon of dualism itself turned out to be a deep shock, but the fact that a particle in an experiment manifests itself as a corpuscle only when an observer looks at it. Those. quanta appear as particles only when we look at them. For example, when an electron is not observed, it always manifests itself as a wave. Based on the properties of holograms, Beom suggested that the interaction of material particles – is nothing more than an illusion. In fact, they are still a whole. Thus, the Universe itself is a very complex illusion. Material objects are combinations of holographic frequencies. «The principle of the hologram» «*everything in every part*» allows us to take a completely new approach to the issue of organization and orderliness, says Professor Bom. Explicit superluminal interaction between particles (the principle of quantum nonlocality) tells us that there is a deeper level of reality hidden from us. Separate, we see these particles only because we see only a part of reality».

3. $SP\Phi$ -SYMMETRY

$SP\Phi$ -symmetry is a combined three-component symmetry of similarity of objects, phenomena and processes at different scale levels of matter, which is a characteristic feature of holography. With its help, in the theory of infinite nesting of matter, the similarity of matter levels is described and the invariance of the physical laws at these levels is proved. With the help of $SP\Phi$ -symmetry, the meaning of the scale dimension is clarified. The $SP\Phi$ -symmetry theorem was proved by Sergey Fedosin in 1999. [15] In the combined transformation of $SP\Phi$, the invariance of physical laws appears as a result of transitions from one scale level of matter to other levels of matter. To go from one level of matter to another using $SP\Phi$, it is necessary to simultaneously

perform the transformation of speeds S , the transformation of sizes (scales) P and the transformation of masses Φ . The values of S , P and Φ are fixed with the help of the corresponding coefficients of similarity between the levels where the transition takes place. Since objects of a lower level of matter are part of an object of a higher scale level of matter, this allows, based on the physical laws and equations of the state of matter, to derive relations between the similarity coefficients S , P and Φ . After substitution of the new variables in the Lagrange function, which determines the laws of motion of the physical system, taking into account the $SP\Phi$ transformation, the Lagrange function does not change its form. This means that physical laws do not change during transitions between different levels of matter, and the corresponding phenomena occur similarly to each other. In particular, at each level of matter, you can enter your own Dirac constant as a characteristic angular momentum (spin) and quantum of action of typical objects, and also write your own Heisenberg uncertainty principle. Another example are stellar constants corresponding to the level of stars. If the system of physical units CGS perform similarity transformation for the masses, the size and speed, it turns out that it is necessary to convert to Newton's law of attraction not only weight and size but also the constant of gravitation. At the same time, in the CGS system of units, the electric constant is 1 and the transformation concerns only forces, charges, and dimensions. This means that during the transition to atomic systems, ordinary gravity is replaced by strong gravity and a new constant appears - the constant of strong gravity. Strong gravity is responsible for the integrity of elementary particles, including nucleons, and in the gravitational model of strong interaction is an integral part of the strong interaction.. [16] The transition to atomic systems is accompanied by a significant increase not only of gravity, but also of electromagnetic fields operating near elementary particles. In this case, the value of the electric constant does not change either in the GHS or in any other system of physical quantities. According to the substantial model of the neutron and the substantial model of the proton, the equation of state of matter of nucleons is similar to the equation of state of matter of neutron stars. Similar are the dependencies of mass on the radius. $SP\Phi$ symmetry allows one to understand the dependences arising between the mass and the electric charge of the proton, substantiate the quark quasiparticle model, approach the essence of the gravitational and electromagnetic forces in the framework of the Le Sage gravity theory.

4. $SP\Phi$ -DETERMINISM

So, as we found out, between the planet and its atoms there is a similarity coefficient, which indicates an intersystem (at least energy-informational) interaction between objects of various scale levels of objective reality. We will continue the analysis and try to find out if intervention

in the intersystem interaction process is possible. Synthesis of the provisions of the SPΦ-symmetry theorem [15] [16], the virial theorem [5], and the principle of determinism [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], In particular, the causal interpretation of quantum mechanics logically leads to SPF-determinism, which can be formulated as follows:

SPΦ-determinism is a natural interrelation and causal interdependence of phenomena, types and forms of matter of various scale levels of being:

$$\frac{\text{planet}}{\text{OSF}} \leftarrow \text{SP}\Phi_{\text{determ.}} \rightarrow \frac{\text{atom}}{\text{OAF}}$$

This definition leads to a series of consecutive conclusions.

1. In accordance with the SPΦ-symmetry theorem, the virial theorem and the principle of determinism, the planet is formed by a set of atomic cell values.
2. The principle of SPΦ-determinism follows from an analysis of the causality of the principle [17] [18] and the theorem on SPΦ-symmetry [15], and establishes a vast range of influence, the lower limit of which is the Planck length l_p , and the upper limit the scale of large Dirac numbers [19] [20].
3. If, in the concepts of D. Bohm and Gerardus T'Hooft, the principle of holographism means either a one-sided direction of the process – from implicative reality to explicative, or their informational interchange only, that SPΦ-determinism already implies active both informational I and energy-force $E-F$ interaction of phenomena, types and forms of matter of various scale levels of explicative being:

$$\frac{\text{core of the planet}}{\text{OSF}} \leftarrow \begin{pmatrix} \text{E} \\ \text{I} \\ \text{F} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \frac{\text{nucleus of an atom}}{\text{OAF}}$$

4. SPΦ-determinism, in particular, suggests that the impact on the OAF has a similar-reverse (I-E-F) effect on the OSF.

5. The mechanism of interaction forces SPΦ-determinism is supposedly non-local character.

6. SPΦ-determinism, Newton's third law and the law of conservation of momentum resulting from it ($\vec{F}_2 \rightarrow 1 = -\vec{F}_1 \rightarrow 2$) [21] [22] claim that the impact on the atom (split) as part of a whole, leading to excitation forces and counteracting violation of integrity (of symmetry) of the entire OSF gravi-electromagnetic (GEM)-field planet that, as a consequence, provokes the following:

- 1 – changes in the spin-orbital characteristics of the planet;
- 2 – deformation (splitting) of the structure of a gravi-electromagnetic field [1] of the planet;
- 3 – the inverse excitement of the global opposition forces.

Such an active influence is unambiguously atomic fission technology: the testing of nuclear weapons, the operation of nuclear power plants, the Large Hadron Collider and other charged particle accelerators. And the numerous abnormal natural phenomena observed today are definitely the result of the technology of splitting the atom and elementary particles, and not the geological period, or the result of the greenhouse effect, and certainly not the «game of the blind forces of nature».

SPΦ-determinism reveals a close causal relationship between the core of the planet and the nucleus of the atom (per se of all the nuclei of the atoms making up the substance and the space-sphere of the torsion field of the Earth $E_0 \sum_i mc^2$), which again confirms the principle of

holographism – «*everything in every part*», in connection with which the notation of the principle of SPΦ-determinism should take on a form more consistent with its essence:

$$\overbrace{\mathbf{E}_0 \text{ core of the planet}}^{\text{OSF}} \left(\text{as a holographic projector of the space-time continuum of matter and fields of the planet} \right) \leftarrow \text{SP}\Phi\text{determinism} \rightarrow \overbrace{\mathbf{E}_0 \sum_i \text{substance of the planet and its fields}}^{\text{OAF}} \left(\text{elementary particles of the} \right),$$

that allows you to trace and comprehend a number of events and phenomena of recent years.

7. According to SPΦ-determinism, the counteracting forces excited by the splitting of an atom lead to the following:

- 1 – splitting, 2 – warming, and 3 – the destabilization (swinging) of the planet's core and 4 – change the orbital characteristics of the planet, in particular, to reduce the orbital speed. If

climate change can still be logically explained by a change in the geological period, then how to explain the anomalous buildup of the planet's core and other modern natural anomalies?

I. Splitting the core of the planet as a generator of the GEM-field [1] leads to:

1 – weakening and splitting the main dipole magnetic field of the planet into fragments, which leads to further 2 – local perturbations and deformations of the magnetic field, which in turn strengthens the atmospheric (hurricanes) and hydrospheric (splitting of the golfstream) perturbations (in one geographic region it can snow and stand unbearable heat).

II. Warming up and swinging the core of the planet provoke

1 – magma fluidity, which leads to 2 – the growth of volcanic activity, 3 – the shift of lithospheric plates and earthquakes.

The warming up and swinging of the planet's core also provoke an increase in the amount of water: water can form in the bowels of the Earth under certain extreme conditions – high temperature and pressure, which are present in the upper layers of the mantle – with increasing temperature and pressure, quartz is able to react with hydrogen, as a result silicon hydrides and liquid water are obtained. This water also becomes an additional trigger for seismic activity. [23].

III. Warming up also leads to 5 – an increase in soil temperature (that is, the planet is initially heated from the bottom) and then the atmosphere, which in turn provokes 6 – atmospheric and hydrospheric perturbations (hurricanes, changes in ocean currents, an increase in the temperature of the world basin)

IV. The splitting of the main dipole magnetic field of the planet in combination with the movements of the earth's crust additionally leads to 7 – activation and an increase in the number of anomalous zones, which in turn leads to 8 – an increase in the number of local temporal spatial distortions (disturbances of the natural course of time continuum) and 9 – serious disruptions in the evolutionary biorhythms of flora and fauna [24] [25] [26].

V. The destabilization of the core of the planet, as an element of the solar system, will undoubtedly affect the state of both the other planets in system 10 – the growth of volcanism and the movement of the lithosphere, and the state of the star itself (destabilization of activity).

CONCLUSION

By extracting energy by splitting the atom, we are pushing our planet to the edge of the abyss, even without knowing it, and continue to be surprised at the new and unexpected anomalies of nature and build various assumptions about their cause. Our current knowledge of the process of splitting the atom is limited by the rejection of advanced breakthrough ideas of the holographic nature of the material world and the endless nesting of matter. However, not knowing the law is no excuse. And year after year, as the number of new NPPs put into operation and the capacities of new elementary particle accelerators constantly increasing, the potential of counter forces will only steadily increase. In other words, the number and strength of natural anomalies will definitely increase.

It is not the burning of hydrocarbons and not the geological cycles that trigger climate change and the impending Apocalypse, but the splitting of the atom!

REFERENCES

1. Gainulin M. V. «Need for adjustment of the orbital telescopes and devices visual observation of the automatic interplanetary station according to the second Bohr quantum postulate».
<http://www.scientific-publications.net/en/article/1000985/>
2. Gainulin M. V., Vvedenie v fiziku Vremeni. Ch.1. Otnositel'noe Vremja (Introduction to the physics of Time. Part 1. Relative time), Lambert Academic Publishing, 2014.
3. David De Mille, John Doyle, Gerald Gabrielse, Order of magnitude smaller limit on the electric dipole moment of the electron, 7 Nov. 2013. Available at: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1310.7534>
4. Butusov K. P., Rezonans voln bienij i zakon planetnyh periodov (Resonance waves beat and the law of planetary periods). Journal Russian Physical Thought, Vol. 1, pp. 39-43, 2006.
Available at: <http://www.rusphysics.ru/dissertation/370/>
5. Goldstein H. Classical Mechanics. – 2nd. ed. – Addison–Wesley, 1980
http://www.fisica.net/ebooks/Classical_Mechanics_Goldstein_3ed.pdf
6. Gerard 't Hooft Determinism beneath Quantum Mechanics. 2002
<http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/0212095>
7. Gerard 't Hooft Quantum Mechanics and Determinism. 2001
<http://arxiv.org/abs/hep-th/0105105>
8. Gerard 't Hooft The mathematical basis for deterministic quantum mechanics 2006
<http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/0604008>
9. Gerard 't Hooft Quantum Gravity as a Dissipative Deterministic System 1999
<http://arxiv.org/abs/gr-qc/9903084>
10. Gerard 't Hooft Determinism in Free Bosons 2001
<http://arxiv.org/abs/hep-th/0104080>

11. Gerard 't Hooft Entangled quantum states in a local deterministic theory 2009
<http://arxiv.org/abs/0908.3408>
12. Ramin Zahedi On Discrete Physics: a Perfect Deterministic Structure for Reality - And "The Mathematical Derivation of the Laws of the Fundamental Forces of Nature" 2015
<http://arxiv.org/abs/1501.01373>
13. Butusov K. P., Zolotoe sechenie v Solnechnoj sisteme. Astronomija i nebesnaja mehanika. Serija «Problemy issledovanija Vselennoj» (The golden ratio in Solar system. Astronomy and celestial mechanics. Serie «Problems of research of the Universe»), Vol. 7, pp. 475–500, 1978.
14. Malhotra R., Orbital resonances and chaos in the Solar system. Solar System Formation and Evolution, Brazil, Rio de Janeiro, ASP Conference Series, vol. 149, 1998. Available at:
http://www.lpl.arizona.edu/people/faculty/malhotra_preprints/rio97.pdf
15. Fedosin S.G. $SP\Phi$ -symmetry
Available on: <http://www.wikiznanie.ru/wikipedia/index.php/SP%D0%A4-%D1%81%D0%B8%D0%BC%D0%BC%D0%B5%D1%82%D1%80%D0%B8%D1%8F>
16. Fedosin S.G. Physics and philosophy of similarity from preons to metagalaxies. Perm. «Style-MG». 1999. Available on: <https://payhip.com/b/wGPU>
17. Kuptsov V.I. Determinism and probability, Moscow, Politizdat. 1976. p. 256.
Available on: <http://scientificbook.net/16629-determinizm-i-verojatnost-v-i-kupcov.html>
18. Georg Henrik von Wright Causality and Determinism 1974 The Philosophical Review Vol. 87, No. 1 (Jan., 1978) Available on: <http://philpapers.org/rec/VONCAD-3>
19. P. Caldirola M. Pavsic & E. Recami: Explaining the Large Numbers by a Hierarchy of Universes: A Unified Theory of Strong and Gravitational Interactions. Nuovo Cimento. B 48. 1978. p. 205-271.
20. J. Casado. Connecting Quantum and Cosmic Scales by a Decreasing-Light-Speed Model. 2004. Available on: <http://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0404130>

21. Landau L.D., Lifshits E. M., Theoretical Physics, vol. 1, Mechanics, part. 2 Laws of conservation, paragraph 6, Energy, Moscow, Publisher «Fizmatlit». 2002. p.
Available on: <http://eqworld.ipmnet.ru/ru/library/physics/lectures.htm>
22. Ishlinsky A. Yu., Classical mechanics and inertial forces, Moscow, Publisher «Science», 1987. Available on: <http://padabum.com/d.php?id=35395>
23. Zdenek Futera, Xue Yong, Yuanming Pan, John S. Tse, Niall J. English
Formation and properties of water from quartz and hydrogen at high pressure and temperature
Available on:
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/earth-and-planetary-science-letters/recent-articles>
24. Presman A.S. Electromagnetic fields and wildlife, Moscow, Publisher «Science», 1968.
Available on: <http://en.booklid.org/book/478339>
25. Presman A.S. The ideas of V. I. Vernadsky in modern biology, Moscow, Publisher «Znanie». 1976. Available on: <http://thebook.16mb.com/a67188.php>
26. Schumann Resonance: http://www.hese-project.org/hese-uk/en/papers/schlegel_schumann.pdf